

Fuzzy Grill m -Space and Induced Fuzzy Topology

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Abstract.

The purpose of this paper is to introduce the notions of two operators $\mathcal{O}_{G,N}$ and $\Psi_{G,N}$ induced by fuzzy grill G on a fuzzy m - space. A new fuzzy topology $\tau_{G,N}$ is obtained with the help of non- fuzzy topological space (fuzzy m -space) and the basic properties of the induced topology are studied. Then a sort of suitability condition of fuzzy grill with fuzzy m - space is formulated.

Keywords: Fuzzy grill, $\mathcal{O}_{G,N}$ - operator, $\Psi_{G,N}$ - operator

1. Introduction

The concept of Grill was introduced by Choquet [3] in 1947 since then it has been extensively used by many authors, grill has subsequently turned out to be a very convenient tool for various topological investigations. It is also seen from the literature that in many situations, grill are more effective than certain similar concepts like nets and filters. Chang [2] introduced the notion of fuzzy topology in 1968. In fuzzy setting, the concept of fuzzy grills on fuzzy topological spaces was initiated by Azad [4]. Subsequently Srivastava and Gupta [10] investigated fuzzy basic proximity by use of fuzzy grill. The concept of complete $\mathcal{F}$ grill in an L - merotopy, a concept similar to that of a bunch in the classical theory and an L -merotopy has been introduced by Mona Khare and Rashmi Singh [5,6,7]. In 2010, M. Khare and S. Tiwari studied grill determined L - approach merotopological spaces In 2005, Bhattacharya, M N Mukherjee and S P Sinha have studied fuzzy compactness fuzzy almost compactness via fuzzy grill. Roy and Mukherjee [1] introduced an operator defined by grill on topological spaces. They [9] introduced the operators by fuzzy grill on fuzzy topological showed that it satisfy Kuratowski's closure axioms. In 2010, Sunita Das and M .N. Mukherjee introduced a kind of generalized fuzzy closed sets in terms of fuzzy grill and discussed their basic properties. In 2013[11] S. Modak introduced operators on grill m space.

In the present paper, we have introduced fuzzy m -space and fuzzy grill on fuzzy m -space. We obtained a fuzzy-topology, however fuzzy m -space need not be a fuzzy topological space. Here we have studied certain basic properties of this new induced fuzzy topology.

In section 3, we introduce two fuzzy operators $\mathcal{O}_{G,N}$ and $\Psi_{G,N}$. In section 4, we define a suitability condition which when imposed on fuzzy grill G with fuzzy m -space makes generated fuzzy topology better behaved and applicable. Finally, we undertake a few fuzzy topological concepts for their study in respect of the m -space vis-à-vis the induced topology. Throughout this paper, we used the following definitions.

2. Preliminaries

$$(A + B)(X) = \begin{cases} A(x) + B(x); & \text{if } A(x) + B(x) \leq 1 \\ 1 & \text{; if } A(x) + B(x) > 1 \end{cases}$$

And

$$(A - B)(X) = \begin{cases} A(x) - B(x); & \text{if } A(x) > B(x) \\ 0 & \text{; if } A(x) \leq B(x) \end{cases}$$

$$(A + B)(X) = \begin{cases} A(x) + B(x) - 1; & \text{if } A(x) + B(x) > 1 \\ 0 & \text{; otherwise} \end{cases}$$

A fuzzy set A in a set X is a function on X into the closed unit interval **[0,1]** of the real line. Support of $A = \{x \in X; A(x) > 0\}$ is denoted by *Supp* A. The fuzzy sets in X taking on respectively the constant values 0 and 1 are denoted by 0_X and 1_X respectively. For $A, B \in I^X, A \leq B$ if $A(x) \leq B(x)$ for each $x \in X$. AqB notation means that A is quasi-coincident with B i.e. AqB implies $A(x) + B(x) > 1$ for some $x \in X$. The negations of these statements are denoted by $A\bar{q}B$. A fuzzy singleton or a fuzzy point with support X and value α ($0 < \alpha \leq 1$) denoted by x_α . A is called q -*nbd* of B of BqU for some fuzzy open set U in X with $U \leq A$, if A itself is fuzzy open then it is called an open- q -*nbd* of B. The collection of all open q -*nbd*s of any fuzzy point x_α is denoted by $Q(x_\alpha)$. A subfamily β of the fuzzy topology τ of an fts (X, τ) is a base for τ iff for each fuzzy singleton x_α in (X, τ) and for each open q -*nbd* U of $x_\alpha, x_\alpha qB$ for some $B \in \beta$ with $B \leq U$. x_α is called an adherence point of fuzzy set A if every open q -*nbd* of x_α is a quasi-coincident with A and $Cl(A)$ is the union of all adherence points of A. $M(A)$ is set of molecules of I^X in A. $VM(\downarrow A) = A$, for $A \in I^X$ where $\downarrow A = \{b \in P; \exists a \in A \text{ s.t. } b \leq a\}$, P is a Poset.

3. Fuzzy grill on Fuzzy m-space

Definition 3.1:- A subfamily m of fuzzy sets I^X is called an fuzzy m -space on X if m satisfies the following conditions

1. $0_X \in m, 1_X \in m$
2. If $A, B \in m \Rightarrow A \wedge B \in m$.

Then (I^X, m) is called fuzzy m -space.

Proposition 3.2:- Given a fuzzy m -space $m, M = \{A : \chi_A \in m\}$ is a classical m -space.

Example 3.2.1:- Let $m = \{0_X, 1_X, f, g\}$, where $X = \{a, b, c\}$,
 $f(a) = 1, f(b) = 0, f(c) = 0, g(a) = 0, g(b) = 1, g(c) = 0$. Then m is a fuzzy m -space.

Definition 3.3:- A fuzzy set $A \in I^X$ is called an m -fuzzy open set if $A \in m, B \in I^X$ is called an m -closed set if $1_X - B \in m$.

Definition 3.4:- A sub collection G on I^X is called fuzzy grill on X if G satisfies following conditions.

1. $0_X \notin G$
2. $A \in G, A \leq B \Rightarrow B \in G$ where $B \in I^X$
3. $A, B \in I^X$ and $A \vee B \in G \Rightarrow A \in G$ or $B \in G$.

A fuzzy m -space (I^X, m) with a fuzzy grill G on X is called fuzzy grill m -space and is denoted by (I^X, m, G) .

Example 3.4.1:- Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$. Let G consist 1_X and all fuzzy sets G of X s.t. $0.4 \leq G(a) \leq 1, 0 \leq G(b) \leq 1, 0 \leq G(c) \leq 1$.

G is a fuzzy grill.

Definition 3.5:- $m - q - nbd$:- A is called a $m - qnbd$ of B if BqU for some m -fuzzy open set U in X with $U \leq A$. In addition if A itself is m -fuzzy open then it is called an m -open $qnbd$ of B. We denote the collection of all m open $qnbd$ of x_α by $Q_m(x_\alpha)$

Definition 3.6:- $m - Int(A) \rightarrow m - fuzzy interior$
 $= \bigvee \{ U : U \leq A \text{ s.t. } U \in m \}$

Definition 3.7:- $m - Cl(A) \rightarrow m - fuzzy closure$
 $= A \{ F : F \geq A \text{ s.t. } I_X - F \in m \}$

Definition 3.8:- m -adherence point of fuzzy set A is x_α if every m -open $qnbd$ of x_α is quasi- coincident with A.

Theorem 3.9:- $m - Cl A$ is union of all m -adherence points of A.

Proof:-

First we will prove that $M(\downarrow (m-ClA))$ is just the set of all the m -adherence points if A.

Suppose $x_\lambda \in M(\downarrow (m-ClA))$. For all $U \in Q_m(x_\lambda)$, if $A \leq 1_X - U$, Then $x_\lambda \leq m - Cl(A) \leq m - Cl(1_X - U) = (1_X - U) \Rightarrow U(y) + x_\lambda(y) \leq 1$, for each $y \in X$, But $U \in Q_m(x_\lambda)$ So $x_\lambda(x) + U(x) > 1$, by definition we have **CONTRADICTION**.

So $A \not\leq 1_X - U \Rightarrow U(y) + A(y) > 1$ for some $y \in X \Rightarrow x_\lambda$ is adherent point of A. Conversely, if x_λ is an m -adherent point of A. Let $x_\lambda \not\leq m - Cl A$ but $m - Cl(A) = A \{ F : F \geq A \text{ and } I_X - F \in m \} \Rightarrow x_\lambda \not\leq F$ for some

$F \Rightarrow (I_X - F)(x) + x_\lambda(x) > 1 \Rightarrow I_X - F \in Q_m(x_\lambda)$. Since x_λ is m -adherent point of A and $A \leq m - Cl(I_X - F)(y) + A(y) > I_X$ for some $y \in X \Rightarrow (I_X - F)(y) + F(y) > I_X(y) > 1$,

CONTRADICTION. So $x_\lambda \leq m - Cl(A) = \bigvee M(\downarrow (m - ClA))$. So $M(\downarrow (m - ClA))$ is just set of all m - adherent point of A. We know that $\bigvee M(\downarrow (m - ClA)) = m - ClA$. So $m - ClA$ is union of all m -adherence point of A.

Definition 3.10:- Fuzzy $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}$ - Operator

Let (I^X, m) be a fuzzy m -space and $\mathbf{G}$ be a fuzzy grill on X . A mapping $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m} : I^X \rightarrow I^X$ denoted by $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) = \mathcal{O}(A) = \bigvee \{ x_\alpha : A * U \in \mathbf{G} \text{ for all } U \in Q_m(x_\alpha) \}$. Where A is a fuzzy set, $\mathcal{O}$ is called operator associated with fuzzy grill $\mathbf{G}$ and fuzzy m - structure on I^X

Proposition 3.11:- Let $(I^X, m, \mathbf{G})$ be a fuzzy grill m -space.

- (i) If $\mathbf{G}$ be a fuzzy grill and $G \in \mathbf{G}$, Then $\mathcal{O}(G) = O_X$
- (ii) $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(O_X) = O_X$
- (iii) For $A, B \in I^X$, if $A \leq B \Rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B)$
- (iv) If $\mathbf{G}_1$ and $\mathbf{G}_2$ are two fuzzy grills on fuzzy m -space (X, m) with $\mathbf{G}_1 \leq \mathbf{G}_2$. Then $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_1, m}(A) \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_2, m}(A)$ for $A \in I^X$.
- (v) For $A, B \in I^X$, $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A \vee B) = \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \vee \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B)$

Proof:-

(i) Let $x_\alpha \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(G) \Rightarrow$ for all $U \in Q_m(x_\alpha)$, $G * U \in \mathbf{G}$, But $U \leq I_X \Rightarrow G * U \leq G \Rightarrow G \in \mathbf{G}$, $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}}(G) = O_X$

(ii) $O_X \in \mathbf{G}$, $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(O_X) = O_X$

(iii) $x_\alpha \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \Rightarrow$ for all $U \in Q_m(x_\alpha)$, $A * U \in \mathbf{G}$, Now $A \leq B \Rightarrow A * U \leq B * U$, Thus for all $U \in Q_m(x_\alpha)$, $B * U \in \mathbf{G}$, So $x_\alpha \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B)$

(iv) Let $x_\alpha \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_1, m}(A)$, Then for all $U \in Q_m(x_\alpha)$, $A * U \in \mathbf{G}_1 \leq \mathbf{G}_2 \Rightarrow x_\alpha \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_2, m}(A) \Rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_1, m}(A) \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_2, m}(A)$

(v) $A \leq A \vee B \Rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A \vee B)$

$B \leq A \vee B \Rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B) \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A \vee B)$

$\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \vee \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B) \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A \vee B)$. Conversely we will prove that $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A \vee B) \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \vee \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B)$

Let $x_\alpha \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \vee \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B) \Rightarrow \exists U, V \in Q_m(x_\alpha)$ s.t. $A * U \in \mathbf{G}$ and $B * V \in \mathbf{G}$, Then $U \vee V \in Q_m(x_\alpha) \Rightarrow$

$(A \vee B) * (U \vee V) \leq (A * U) \vee (B * V) \in \mathbf{G}$, Thus $x_\alpha \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A \vee B)$. So $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A \vee B) = \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \vee \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B)$.

Proposition 3.12:- Let $(I^X, m, \mathbf{G})$ be fuzzy grill m -space, then

- (i) $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A \vee G) = \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)$ for $G \in \mathbf{G}$
- (ii) $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A) \leq m - Cl(A)$ for $A \in \mathcal{F}^X$.
- (iii) $m - Cl(\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)) \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)$, for $A \in \mathcal{F}^X$
- (iv) $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)$ is m -closed set for $A \in \mathcal{F}^X$

Proof: - For $A \in \mathcal{F}^X, G \in \mathbf{G}$

- (i) $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A \vee G) = \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A) \vee \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}}(G) = \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A) \vee \mathcal{O}_X = \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)$
- (ii) Let $(x_\alpha) \leq m - Cl(A)$, Then $\exists$ an m - open q nbd U of x_α in X s.t. $U \bar{q} A$ i.e. $A(y) + U(y) \leq 1$ for each $y \in X \Rightarrow A * U = \mathcal{O}_X \in \mathbf{G} \Rightarrow x_\alpha \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A) \Rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A) \leq m - Cl(A)$
- (iii) Let $x_\alpha \leq m - Cl(\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A))$ and $U \in \mathcal{Q}_m(x_\alpha) \Rightarrow (\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)) \bar{q} U$, then $\exists y \in X$ s.t. $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)(y) + U(y) > 1$, Let $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)(y) = t \Rightarrow y_1 \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)$ and $U \in \mathcal{Q}_m(y_1) \Rightarrow A * U \in \mathbf{G} \Rightarrow x_\alpha \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A) \Rightarrow m - Cl(\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)) \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)$
- (iv) $m - Cl(\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)) \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)$, By definition of $m - Cl$, $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A) \leq m - Cl(\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)) \Rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A) = m - Cl(\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A))$

Definition 3.13:- Let $\mathbf{G}$ be a fuzzy grill on fuzzy m -space $(\mathcal{F}^X, m)$ we define $\psi = \psi_{\mathbf{G}_M}, \mathcal{F}^X \rightarrow \mathcal{F}^X$ by $\psi_{\mathbf{G}_M} A = A \vee \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)$ for $A \in \mathcal{F}^X$

Proposition 3.14:- $\psi_{\mathbf{G}_M}$ is a Kuratowski closure operator

Definition 3.15:- Let $(\mathcal{F}^X, m, \mathbf{G})$ be fuzzy grill m -space, then $\tau_{\mathbf{G}_M} = \{U \in \mathcal{F}^X : \psi_{\mathbf{G}_M}(I_X - U) = (I_X - U)\}$ is fuzzy topology on 1_X where for $A \in \mathcal{F}^X, \psi_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A) = A \vee \psi_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A) = \tau_{\mathbf{G}_M} - Cl(A)$

Theorem 3.16:- if $\mathbf{G}_1$ and $\mathbf{G}_2$ are two fuzzy grills on $\mathcal{F}^X$ with $\mathbf{G}_1 \leq \mathbf{G}_2$, Then $\tau_{\mathbf{G}_2, M} \leq \tau_{\mathbf{G}_1, M}$

Proof:-

Let $U \in \tau_{\mathbf{G}_2, M} \Rightarrow \tau_{\mathbf{G}_2, M} - Cl(I_X - U) = \psi_{\mathbf{G}_2, M}(I_X - U) = I_X - U \Rightarrow (I_X - U) = (I_X - U) \vee \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_2, M}(I_X - U) \Rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_2, M}(I_X - U) \leq (I_X - U)$, but $\mathbf{G}_1 \leq \mathbf{G}_2$ So $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_1, M}(I_X - U) \leq (I_X - U) \Rightarrow \psi_{\mathbf{G}_1, M}(I_X - U) = (I_X - U)$. $(I_X - U)$ is $\tau_{\mathbf{G}_1, M}$ -closed $\Rightarrow U \in \tau_{\mathbf{G}_1, M} \Rightarrow \tau_{\mathbf{G}_2, M} \leq \tau_{\mathbf{G}_1, M}$

Proposition 3.17:- Let $\mathbf{G}$ be fuzzy grill on $(\mathcal{F}^X, m)$ and $B \in \mathbf{G}$. Then B is closed in $(\mathcal{F}^X, \tau_{\mathbf{G}_M})$.

Proof:- Since $B \in \mathbf{G} \Rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(B) = \mathcal{O}_X$, Then $\tau_{\mathbf{G}_M} - Cl(B) = B \vee \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(B) = B$, B is $\tau_{\mathbf{G}_M}$ -closed.

Proposition 3.18:- For any fuzzy subset A of a fuzzy m -space $(\mathcal{F}^X, m)$ and fuzzy grill $\mathbf{G}$ on $\mathcal{F}^X$, $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)$ is $\tau_{\mathbf{G}_M}$ -closed.

Proof:- For $A \in \mathcal{F}^X, \psi_{\mathbf{G}_M}(\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)) = \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A) \vee \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)) = \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A) \Rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G}_M}(A)$ is $\tau_{\mathbf{G}_M}$ -closed.

Remark 3.19:- Let $(\mathcal{F}^X, m, \mathbf{G})$ be fuzzy grill m -fuzzy grill space for two fuzzy grills $\mathbf{G}_1$ and $\mathbf{G}_2$, $\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2$ is fuzzy grill on X but $\mathbf{G}_1 \cap \mathbf{G}_2$ may not be a fuzzy grill on X .

Example:- Let $X = \{a_1, a_2\}, M = \{\mathcal{O}_X, 1_X, A, B\}$. Where $A(a_1) = 0, A(a_2) = 0.5, B(a_1) = 0.6, B(a_2) = 0$. Then $(\mathcal{F}^X, m)$ is fuzzy m -space. Let $\mathbf{G}_1$ consist of 1_X and all fuzzy sets G_1 of X s.t. $0.4 \leq G_1(a_1) \leq 1, 0 \leq G_1(a_2) \leq 1$. Then $\mathbf{G}_1$ is a fuzzy grill. Let $\mathbf{G}_2$ consist of 1_X and all fuzzy sets G_2 of X s.t. $0 \leq G_2(a_1) \leq 1, 0.2 \leq G_2(a_2) \leq 1 \Rightarrow$ Then $\mathbf{G}_2$ is a fuzzy grill. Let C, D are two fuzzy sets s.t. $C(a_1) = 0.4, C(a_2) = 0, D(a_1) = 0, D(a_2) = 0.3, C \in \mathbf{G}_1$ but $C \notin \mathbf{G}_2, d \in \mathbf{G}_1$ but $d \notin \mathbf{G}_2$. Let $A^* = C \vee D, A^*(a_1) = 0.4, A^*(a_2) = 0.3, A^* \in \mathbf{G}_1 \cap \mathbf{G}_2$ but neither $B \in \mathbf{G}_1 \cap \mathbf{G}_2$ nor $C \in \mathbf{G}_1 \cap \mathbf{G}_2$

Theorem 3.20:- Let $(\mathcal{F}^X, m, \mathbf{G})$ be fuzzy grill m -space and $\mathbf{G}_1, \mathbf{G}_2$ be two fuzzy grill, $\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2 = \{G_1 \wedge G_2 / G_1 \in \mathbf{G}_1, G_2 \in \mathbf{G}_2 \text{ and } G_1 \leq G_2 \text{ or } G_2 \leq G_1\}$

Then $\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2$ is a fuzzy grill m -space.

Proof:- For $A, B, C \in \mathcal{F}^X$

- (i) $\mathcal{O}_X \in \mathbf{G}_1, \mathbf{G}_2 \Rightarrow \mathcal{O}_X \in \mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2$
- (ii) Let $A \in \mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2 \Rightarrow A = G_1 \wedge G_2$ where $G_1 \in \mathbf{G}_1, G_2 \in \mathbf{G}_2$ and at least one is contained in other. Suppose, Let $G_1 \leq G_2 \Rightarrow G_1 \wedge G_2 = G_1$. Take $A \leq B, G_1 \wedge G_2 \leq B \Rightarrow G_1 \leq B, G_1 \in \mathbf{G}_1 \Rightarrow B \in \mathbf{G}_1$ Now $B = B \wedge 1_X \in \mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2$ and $A \leq B \Rightarrow B \in \mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2$

(iii) Let $A = B \vee C \in \mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2$, Then $A = B \vee C = G_1 \wedge G_2$ where $G_1 \in \mathbf{G}_1$, $G_2 \in \mathbf{G}_2$ and $G_1 \leq G_2$ or $G_2 \leq G_1$. Suppose, $G_1 \leq G_2$, So $A = G_1 \wedge G_2 = G_1 \in \mathbf{G}_1$, $G_1 \leq G_2 \in \mathbf{G}_1$, $B \vee C = G_1 \in \mathbf{G}_1$. So either $B \in \mathbf{G}_1$ or $C \in \mathbf{G}_1$.
 if $B \in \mathbf{G}_1 \Rightarrow B = B \wedge 1_X \Rightarrow B \in \mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2$, if $C \in \mathbf{G}_1 \Rightarrow C = C \wedge 1_X \Rightarrow C \in \mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2$

Theorem 3.21:- Let $\mathbf{G}_1$ and $\mathbf{G}_2$ be two fuzzy grill on fuzzy m - space (I^X, m) , then for any fuzzy set $A \in I^X$.

- (a) $\phi_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A) \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}_2 \wedge \mathbf{G}_1}(A) = \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \vee \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A)$
- (b) $\phi_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A) \wedge \phi_{\mathbf{G}_2 \wedge \mathbf{G}_1}(A) \leq \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A)$

Proof:- For $A \in I^X$

(a) $\mathbf{G}_1, \mathbf{G}_2 \leq \mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2 \Rightarrow \phi_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A) \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}_2 \wedge \mathbf{G}_1}(A) \leq \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A)$. Conversely Let $x_\alpha \notin \phi_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A) \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}_2 \wedge \mathbf{G}_1}(A) \Rightarrow x_\alpha \notin \phi_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A)$ and $x_\alpha \notin \phi_{\mathbf{G}_2 \wedge \mathbf{G}_1}(A)$. Now $x_\alpha \notin \phi_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A) \Rightarrow \exists U_1 \in \phi_M(x_\alpha)$ s.t. $A * U_1 \in \mathbf{G}_1$ and $x_\alpha \notin \phi_{\mathbf{G}_2 \wedge \mathbf{G}_1}(A) \Rightarrow \exists U_2 \in \phi_M(x_\alpha)$ s.t. $A * U_2 \in \mathbf{G}_2$. Then $A * (U_1 \wedge U_2) \in \mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2$ where $U_1 \wedge U_2 \in \phi_M(x_\alpha)$. So that $x_\alpha \notin \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A)$. Thus $\phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A) \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A) \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}_2 \wedge \mathbf{G}_1}(A)$. Thus $\phi_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A) \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}_2 \wedge \mathbf{G}_1}(A) = \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A)$.

(b) Let $Y_B \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A) \wedge \phi_{\mathbf{G}_2 \wedge \mathbf{G}_1}(A)$ Then $Y_B \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A)$ and $Y_B \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}_2 \wedge \mathbf{G}_1}(A) \Rightarrow$ for each $U \in \mathbf{G}_1, \mathbf{G}_2$. Let $A * U = G \Rightarrow G \in \mathbf{G}_1, G \in \mathbf{G}_2$ and $G \leq G$ and $G = G \wedge G \in \mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2, A * U \in \mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2, Y_B \leq \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A)$

Example 3.21.1:- Let $X = \{a, b\}, m = \{O_X, 1_X, A, B\}$, where $A(a) = 0.5, A(b) = 0.6, B(a) = B(b) = 0.3$. Then (I^X, m) is fuzzy m -space. Let $\mathbf{G}_1$ consist of all fuzzy sets G_1 of X s.t. $0.6 \leq G_1(a) \leq 1$ and $0 \leq G_1(b) \leq 1$. Let $\mathbf{G}_2$ consist of all fuzzy sets G_2 in X s.t. $0 \leq G_2(a) \leq 1$ and $0.1 \leq G_2(b) \leq 1$. Let $\mathbf{G}_1, \mathbf{G}_2$ are two fuzzy grills on X then $\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2$ is also a fuzzy grill. We see that $b_{0.4} \leq \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A)$ since for each $U \in \phi_M(b_{0.4}), U(b) > 0.6 \Rightarrow (A * U)(a) > 0.1, (A * U)(b) > 0.2 (A * U) \in \mathbf{G}_2$. Hence $A * U \in \mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2 \Rightarrow b_{0.4} \leq \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A)$. We take $V = 1_X$. Then $(A * V)(a) = 0.5, (A * V)(b) = 0.6 \Rightarrow A * V \in \mathbf{G}_1 \Rightarrow b_{0.4} \notin \phi_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A) \Rightarrow b_{0.4} \notin \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A) \wedge \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_1}(A)$. Hence $\phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A) \not\leq \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(A) \wedge \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_1}(A)$.

Theorem 3.22:- Let $\mathbf{G}_1$ and $\mathbf{G}_2$ be two fuzzy grills on (I^X, m) , then $\tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} = \tau_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \cap \tau_{\mathbf{G}_2} = \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}$

Proof:- Since $\mathbf{G}_1, \mathbf{G}_2 \subseteq \mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2 \Rightarrow \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \subseteq \tau_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \cap \tau_{\mathbf{G}_2}$

Conversely, Let $V \in \tau_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \cap \tau_{\mathbf{G}_2} \Rightarrow V \in \tau_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}$ and $V \in \tau_{\mathbf{G}_2} \Rightarrow \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(1_X - V) \leq 1_X - V$ and $\phi_{(\mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_1}(1_X - V) \leq 1_X - V \Rightarrow \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(1_X - V) \vee \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_1}(1_X - V) \leq (1_X - V) \Rightarrow \phi_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}(1_X - V) \leq 1_X - V \Rightarrow V \in \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}$.

Thus $\tau_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \cap \tau_{\mathbf{G}_2} \subseteq \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \Rightarrow \tau_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \cap \tau_{\mathbf{G}_2} \subseteq \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}$. Now we will prove $\tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} = \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}$. Now $\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2 \subseteq \mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2 \Rightarrow \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \subseteq \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}$. Since $\mathbf{G}_1, \mathbf{G}_2 \subseteq \mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2 \Rightarrow \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \subseteq \tau_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}, \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_1} \subseteq \tau_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}, \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \subseteq \tau_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \cap \tau_{\mathbf{G}_2}$.

Thus $\tau_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \cap \tau_{\mathbf{G}_2} = \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \subseteq \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \subseteq \tau_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \cap \tau_{\mathbf{G}_2} \Rightarrow \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \cup \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} = \tau_{\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2} \cap \tau_{\mathbf{G}_2} = \tau_{(\mathbf{G}_1 \wedge \mathbf{G}_2) \wedge \mathbf{G}_2}$

Example 3.22.1:- In (I^X, m) the trivial F- grill is $I^X \setminus \{O_X\}$. We take $\mathbf{G} = I^X \setminus \{O_X\} \Rightarrow$ for $A \in I^X$, Then we get $\phi_{\mathbf{G} \wedge \mathbf{G}}(A) = m - Cl(A), \psi_{\mathbf{G} \wedge \mathbf{G}}(A) = A \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G} \wedge \mathbf{G}}(A) = m - Cl(A)$. Thus $m = \tau_{\mathbf{G} \wedge \mathbf{G}}$.

Theorem 3.23:- Let $(I^X, m, \mathbf{G})$ be fuzzy grill m -space for $A, B \in I^X, A - (A - B) \leq B$

Proof:- Here two cases will arise for any $Y \in X$, for $A, B \in I^X$

Case 1:- If $A(Y) \leq B(Y), (A - B)(Y) = 0 \Rightarrow (A - (A - B))(Y) = A(Y) \leq B(Y) \Rightarrow A - (A - B) \leq B$

Case 2 :- $A(Y) > B(Y) \Rightarrow [A - (A - B)](Y) = A(Y) - [A(Y) - B(Y)] = B(Y)$. In both case $[A - (A - B)](Y) \leq B(Y) \Rightarrow A - (A - B) \leq B$

Theorem 3.24:- Let $(I^X, m, \mathbf{G})$ be fuzzy grill m -space and $\mathbf{G}$ be a fuzzy grill on X . Then $\beta(\mathbf{G}, m) = \{V - A : V \in m \text{ and } A \in \mathbf{G}\}$ is fuzzy open base for $\tau_{\mathbf{G} \wedge \mathbf{G}}$

Proof:- First we show that $\beta(\mathbf{G}, m)$ is a sub collection of $\tau_{\mathbf{G} \wedge \mathbf{G}}$. Let $U \in \beta(\mathbf{G}, m) \Rightarrow U = V - A$ s.t. $V \in m, A \in \mathbf{G}$. We will prove that $\phi(1_X - U) \leq 1_X - U$. Let $\exists$ a fuzzy point x_α s.t. $x_\alpha \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G} \wedge \mathbf{G}}(1_X - U)$ - (i)
 But $x_\alpha \not\leq (1_X - U)$ - (ii)

(i) implies that for each $W \in Q_M(x_\alpha)$ $W + (1_X - U) - 1_X \in \mathbf{G}$, $W - U \in \mathbf{G}$ - (a), $W - (V - A) \in \mathbf{G}$ - (iii), By (ii) $x_\alpha \notin (1_X - U) \Rightarrow \alpha > (1_X - U)(X) = 1 - (V - A)(X) \Rightarrow \alpha + V(X) > 1 + A(X) \geq 1$. In fact $V(X) \leq A(X)$ is not possible. (Since in that case $(V - A)(X) = 0$ so $1 - (V - A)(X) = 1 - 0 < \alpha$), So $V(X) > A(X)$ and $(V - A)(X) = V(X) - A(X)$, Then $\alpha > (1 - (V - A)(X)) = 1 - V(X) + A(X) \Rightarrow \alpha + V(X) > 1 + A(X)$, Thus $V \in Q_M(x_\alpha)$, By (ii) $V - (V - A) \in \mathbf{G}$, $V - (V - A) \leq A$ by above theorem $\Rightarrow A \in \mathbf{G}$ CONTRADICTION to $A \notin \mathbf{G}$, Thus $\beta(\mathbf{G}, m)$ is sub collection of $\tau_{\mathbf{G},M}$. Next, Let x_α be any fuzzy point in (I^X, m) and U be an m - open q nbd of x_α in $(I^X, \tau_{\mathbf{G},M})$, Then by def. of q nbd $\exists$ a $B \in \tau_{\mathbf{G},M}$ s.t. $x_\alpha q B$ and $B \leq U \Rightarrow 1_X - B$ is $\tau_{\mathbf{G},M}$ - closed and $\varphi(1_X - B) = 1_X - B \Rightarrow \emptyset(1_X - B) \leq 1_X - B$, $x_\alpha \notin \emptyset(1_X - B) \Rightarrow \exists$ a m -open q nbd V of x_α in (X, m) s.t. $(1_X - B) * V \in \mathbf{G}$, By (a) $V - B \in \mathbf{G}$, We will show that $x_\alpha q [V - (V - B)]$, Since $x_\alpha q B$ and $x_\alpha q V$, We have $\alpha + B(X) > 1$, $\alpha + V(X) > 1$, Then if $V(X) \leq B(X)$, we have $\alpha + V(X) - (V - B)(X) \Rightarrow \alpha + B(X) > 1$. Thus we have for each fuzzy point x_α in $(I^X, \tau_{\mathbf{G},M})$ and for each m - open q nbd V of x_α in $(X, \tau_{\mathbf{G},M})$, $\exists V - (V - B) \in \beta(\mathbf{G}, m)$ s.t. $V - (V - B) \leq U$ and $x_\alpha q (V - (V - B))$, $\beta(\mathbf{G}, m)$ is a base of $\tau_{\mathbf{G},M}$.

Corollary 3.24.1:- For any fuzzy m -space $m \subseteq \beta(\mathbf{G}, m) \subseteq \tau_{\mathbf{G},M}$

Example 3.24.2:- Let $(I^X, m, \mathbf{G})$ be fuzzy grill m -space

Take $\mathbf{G} = I^X \setminus \{O_X\}$ Then $\tau_{\mathbf{G},M} = m$. In Fact for fuzzy basic m -open set $B = V - A$ with $V \in m$, $A \in \mathbf{G}$ in $\tau_{\mathbf{G},M}$ We have $A = O_X$, $B = V \in m$, $\beta(\mathbf{G}, m) = m = \tau_{\mathbf{G},M}$

4. Fuzzy m -space suitable with fuzzy grill in fuzzy m -space

Definition 4.1:- Let $\mathbf{G}$ be a fuzzy grill on a fuzzy m -space (I^X, m) . Then m -space is said to be suitable for fuzzy grill $\mathbf{G}$ if for every $A \in I^X$, if corresponding to each $x_\alpha \leq A$, $\exists \alpha U \in Q_M(x_\alpha)$ s.t. $A * U \in \mathbf{G}$, Then $A \in \mathbf{G}$.

Definition 4.2:- For every $A \in I^X$, we define $\tilde{A} = \{x_\alpha \leq A / x_\alpha \notin \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A)\}$

Proposition 4.3:- For any $A \in I^X$

(i) $A = \tilde{A} \vee (A \wedge \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A))$

(ii) $\tilde{A} \wedge \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(\tilde{A}) = O_X$

Theorem 4.4- For a fuzzy grill $\mathbf{G}$ on (X, m) . The following are equivalent

(a) m is suitable for fuzzy grill $\mathbf{G}$

(b) For $A \in I^X$, $A \wedge \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A) = O_X \Rightarrow A \in \mathbf{G}$

(c) $\tilde{A} \in \mathbf{G}$ for $A \in I^X$

(d) For every set A in I^X , if A contains no non empty fuzzy set B with $B \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(B) \Rightarrow$ Then $A \in \mathbf{G}$

(e) For $\tau_{\mathbf{G},M}$ - closed fuzzy set A in X , $\tilde{A} \notin \mathbf{G}$

Proof:-

(a) $\Rightarrow$ (b) Let, $A \wedge \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A) = O_X$ for any given fuzzy set A in X . Now for each fuzzy point $x_\alpha \leq A$, we have $x_\alpha \notin \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A)$. Hence $A \wedge \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A) = O_X$. By definition of $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A)$, $\exists$ some $U \in Q_M(x_\alpha)$ s.t. $A * U \in \mathbf{G}$. Since m is suitable for $\mathbf{G}$, $A \in \mathbf{G}$.

(b) $\Rightarrow$ (c) Let $x_\lambda \notin \tilde{A} \Rightarrow x_\lambda \leq A$ but $x_\lambda \notin \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A)$. Now $\tilde{A} \leq A \Rightarrow$

$\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(\tilde{A}) \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A) \Rightarrow x_\lambda \notin \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A)$. So $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(\tilde{A})(X) = \lambda_0 < \lambda$. Then $x_{\lambda_0} \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(\tilde{A}) \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A)$. But $\lambda_0 < \lambda$, $x_\lambda \leq \tilde{A} \Rightarrow x_{\lambda_0} \leq \tilde{A} \Rightarrow x_{\lambda_0} \notin \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A)$, CONTRADICTION, $\lambda_0 = 0$. $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(\tilde{A})(X) = 0 \Rightarrow \tilde{A} \wedge \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(\tilde{A})(X) = O_X$ By (b) $\tilde{A} \in \mathbf{G}$.

(c) $\Rightarrow$ (d) Let $A \in I^X$ which contains no non empty fuzzy set B s.t. $B \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(B)$. We know that $A = \tilde{A} \vee (A \wedge \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A)) \Rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A) = \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(\tilde{A}) \vee (\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A \wedge \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A)))$, By (c) $\tilde{A} \in \mathbf{G} \Rightarrow \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(\tilde{A}) = O_X$. We have $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A) = O_X \vee (\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A \wedge \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A))) = (\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A \wedge \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A)))$, But $(A \wedge \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A)) \leq A \wedge \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A) \leq \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A) = (\mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A \wedge \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A))) \Rightarrow (A \wedge \mathcal{O}_{\mathbf{G},M}(A)) = O_X \Rightarrow A \in \mathbf{G}$

(d) $\Rightarrow$ (c) Let $A \in F^X, \tilde{A} = \{x_\alpha \leq A / x_\alpha \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)\}$, We claim that $\tilde{A}$ does not contain any non empty fuzzy set B s.t. $B \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B)$. Then by $\tilde{A} \notin \mathbf{G}$ if possible, Let B be non empty fuzzy set contained in $\tilde{A}$ s.t. $B \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B)$. Let $x_\alpha \leq B \Rightarrow x_\alpha \leq \tilde{A} \Rightarrow x_\alpha \leq A$ but $x_\alpha \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)$. But $B \leq \tilde{A} \Rightarrow x_\alpha \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B) \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(\tilde{A}) \Rightarrow x_\alpha \leq \tilde{A} \wedge \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(\tilde{A}) = \mathbf{O}_X$, CONTRADICTION.

(c) $\Rightarrow$ (e) $\tilde{A} \notin \mathbf{G}$ for $A \in F^X$, Then $\tilde{A} \notin \mathbf{G}$ for A - $\tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}$ - closed set.

(e) $\Rightarrow$ (a) Let A be any fuzzy set in X with the property that for every fuzzy point $x_\alpha \leq A, \exists a U \in \mathcal{Q}_m(x_\alpha)$ s.t. $A * U \in \mathbf{G} \Rightarrow x_\alpha \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A), B = A \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \Rightarrow \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(\phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A), \tau_{\mathbf{G}, m} - Cl(B) = \psi(B) = B \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B) = B, B$ is $\tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}$ - closed $\Rightarrow \tilde{B} \in \mathbf{G}$, Let $Y_\alpha \leq \tilde{B} \Rightarrow Y_\alpha \leq B$ but $Y_\alpha \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)$, As $B = A \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A), Y_\alpha \leq A, \tilde{B} \leq A, x_\alpha \leq A$ Then $x_\alpha \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B) \Rightarrow x_\alpha \leq \tilde{B} \Rightarrow A \leq \tilde{B} \Rightarrow A = \tilde{B} \in \mathbf{G}, A \in \mathbf{G}$

Theorem 4.5:- Let (F^X, m) be a fuzzy m space, then following are equivalent (a) m – space is suitable for fuzzy grill $\mathbf{G}$

(b) For $A \in F^X, A \wedge \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) = \mathbf{O}_X \Rightarrow \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) = \mathbf{O}_X$

(c) For $A \in F^X, \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(\tilde{A}) = \mathbf{O}_X$

(d) For $A \in F^X, \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A \wedge \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)$

Proof:-

(a) $\Rightarrow$ (b) follows from Theorem 4.4.

(b) $\Rightarrow$ (c) Let $A \in F^X$, using Theorem 4.3 $\tilde{A} \wedge \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(\tilde{A}) = \mathbf{O}_X \Rightarrow \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(\tilde{A}) = \mathbf{O}_X$.

(c) $\Rightarrow$ (d) Let $A \in F^X$, then by proposition 4.3, $A = \tilde{A} \vee (A \wedge \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)) \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(\tilde{A}) \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A \wedge \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A \wedge \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A))$

(d) $\Rightarrow$ (a) Let $A \in F^X, A \wedge \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) = \mathbf{O}_X$ and by (d) $\phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A \wedge \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A), \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(\mathbf{O}_X) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \mathbf{O}_X = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)$

Theorem 4.6:- If m – space of X is suitable for $\mathbf{G}$, then $\phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}$ is idempotent operator i.e. $\phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(\phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)$ for $A \in F^X$

Proof:- For $A \in F^X, \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A \wedge \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)$ ($\because m$ is suitable for $\mathbf{G} \Rightarrow \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A \wedge \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)) \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(\phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A))$). But $\phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(\phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)) \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)$. So $\phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(\phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)$

Theorem 4.7:- Let (X, m) be a m -space and $\mathbf{G}$ be a fuzzy grill on X s.t. m is suitable for $\mathbf{G}$. Then a fuzzy set A in X - $\tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}$ - closed set if it can be expressed as a union of a fuzzy set which is closed in (X, m) and a fuzzy set which is not in $\mathbf{G}$.

Proof:- Let $A \in F^X$

Let A be $\tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}$ - closed, then $A = A \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \Rightarrow \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \leq A \Rightarrow A = \tilde{A} \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)$. Since m is suitable for $\mathbf{G}, \tilde{A} \notin \mathbf{G}$ and $\phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)$ is m -closed. Conversely Let $A = B \vee C$ where B is m - closed, $C \notin \mathbf{G} \Rightarrow \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B) \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(C) = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B) \vee \mathbf{O}_X = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(B) \leq m - (Cl B) = B \leq A, \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \leq A, A$ is $\tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}$ - closed

Example 4.8:- Let (X, m) be fuzzy m -space and $\mathbf{G}$ be fuzzy grill s.t. m is suitable for $\mathbf{G}$. Let $\sigma = \{\mathcal{O}_X, 1_X\}$ denote fuzzy indiscrete topology on $X \Rightarrow (F^X, \sigma)$ is m -space, So 1_X is only σ - open qnb of every x_α in X . Thus for $A \in F^X, x_\alpha \leq \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \Leftrightarrow A * 1_X \in \mathbf{G} \Leftrightarrow A \in \mathbf{G}$. Thus for $A \in \mathbf{G}, \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) = 1_X$, for every fuzzy set $A \notin \mathbf{G}, \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) = \mathbf{O}_X$. Thus $\psi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) = A \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) = 1_X$ if $A \in \mathbf{G}, \psi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) = A$ if $A \notin \mathbf{G}, \sigma_{\mathbf{G}, m} = \{U / 1 - U \in \mathbf{G}\}$, clearly $\sigma_{\mathbf{G}, m} \leq \tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}$. Since for $V \in \sigma_{\mathbf{G}, m}, 1_X - V \notin \mathbf{G}, (1_X - V)$ is $\tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}$ - closed $\Rightarrow V \in \tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}$ for any (X, m) , we claim that $\tau_{\mathbf{G}, m} = m \cup \sigma_{\mathbf{G}, m}$. Clearly $m \leq \tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}, \sigma_{\mathbf{G}, m} \leq \tau_{\mathbf{G}, m} \Rightarrow m \cup \sigma_{\mathbf{G}, m} \leq \tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}$. Conversely, let $U \in \tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}, 1_X - U = F \vee B$ where F is m -closed and $B \notin \mathbf{G}, U = (1_X - F) \wedge (1_X - B)$ where $(1_X - F)$ is m -open and $1_X - B$ is $\sigma_{\mathbf{G}, m}$ - open. So $U \in m \cup \sigma_{\mathbf{G}, m}$. So $\tau_{\mathbf{G}, m} = m \cup \sigma_{\mathbf{G}, m}$

Theorem 4.9:- Let $\mathbf{G}$ be a fuzzy grill on (X, m) with m is suitable for $\mathbf{G}$. Then $\beta(\mathbf{G}, m)$ is fuzzy topology on X . Hence $\beta(\mathbf{G}, m) = \tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}$

Proof:- $\beta(\mathbf{G}, m) \subseteq \tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}$ (Proved), on the other hand, Let A be $\tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}$ - closed. Then $\tau_{\mathbf{G}, m} - Cl(A) = A \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) = A \Rightarrow \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \leq A$, So $A = \tilde{A} \vee (A \wedge \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)) \Rightarrow A = \tilde{A} \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)$. By definition of $\tilde{A}, \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \wedge \tilde{A} = \mathbf{O}_X$ - by (a). Since m is suitable for $\mathbf{G} \Rightarrow \tilde{A} \notin \mathbf{G}$. Thus $A = \tilde{A} \vee \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)$. Where $\phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)$ is m -closed and $\tilde{A} \notin \mathbf{G}$. We can write $A = \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) + \tilde{A}$ - by (a) $1_X - A = 1_X - [\phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) + \tilde{A}] = [1_X - \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A)] - \tilde{A}$. Where $1_X - \phi_{\mathbf{G}, m}(A) \in m, \tilde{A} \notin \mathbf{G}, 1_X - A \in \beta(\mathbf{G}, m)$. So $\beta(\mathbf{G}, m) = \tau_{\mathbf{G}, m}$

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